

NOMENCLATURE OF PROPOSAL TYPE:

Framework (FRAM), Guideline (GUID), Method (METH), Model (MODE), Tool (TOOL), Arquitecture (ARQU), Algorithm (ALGO), Metamodel (META), Guideline and Tool (GTOO), Guideline and Model (GMOD), Framework and Tool (FTOO), Methodology (METY), Methodology and Tool (MTOO).

NOMENCLATURE OF DISCIPLINE:

Computer Science, Hardware & Architecture (CS, H&A)
 Computer Science, Software Engineering (CS, SE)
 Computer Science, Artificial Intelligence (CS, AI)
 Information Science & Library Science (IS&LS)
 Computer Science, Information Systems (CS, IS)
 Mathematical & Computational Biology (M&CB)
 Computer Science, Theory & Methods (CS, T&M)
 Computer Science, Interdisciplinary Applications (CS, IA)
 Multidisciplinary Sciences (MS)
 Biochemical Research Methods (BRM)
 Engineering, Multidisciplinary (EM)
 Mathematics, Applied (MA)

LIST OF 44 INSTITUTIONS, 17 COUNTRIES, NUMBER OF PAPERS PUBLISHED, DISCIPLINE AND 54 PROPOSAL TYPE IN 2012-2019.

Country	Institution name	Published studies	Cite	Discipline	Proposal types
<i>Argentina</i>	Nacional de Cuyo University	1	[1]	CS, H&A	ALGO
<i>Australia</i>	National ICT Australia Ltd	1	[2]	CS, SE	METH
<i>Austria</i>	Secure Business Austria (SBA Research)	2	[3], [4]	CS, AI IS&LS	MODE, META
	Federal University of Juiz de Fora (UFJF)	3	[5], [6], [7]	CS, IS CS, SE CS, SE	ARQU, ARQU, MODE
<i>Brazil</i>	University of Brasilia	2	[8], [9]	M&CB M&CB	ARQU, TOOL
	Universidade Federal de Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ)	1	[10]	CS, IS	TOOL
	Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro	1	[11]	CS, IS	TOOL
	National Laboratory of Scientific Computing - LNCC	1	[12]	M&CB	TOOL
	Federal University of Pernambuco	1	[13]	CS, SE	META
	Research, Innovation and Dissemination Center for Neuromathematics	1	[14]	CS, T&M	GMOD
<i>Chine</i>	Shanghai University	1	[15]	CS, IS	MODE
	Dongbei University of Finance and EcoNomics	1	[16]	CS, AI	ALGO
<i>France</i>	Université Montpellier 2	1	[17]	CS, IS	FRAM

	INRIA Institute National de Recherche en Informatique et en Automatique	1	[18]	CS, H&A	TOOL
	Inria, Mines Nantes, LINA	1	[19]	CS, H&A	TOOL
	Université Nice Sophia Antipolis/CNRS	1	[20]	CS, IS	MODE
<i>Germany</i>	University of Tübingen	2	[21], [22]	CS, IS M&CB	TOOL, TOOL
	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	2	[23], [24]	CS, IS CS, IS	GTOO, FRAM
	Fraunhofer Institute for Experimental Software Engineering	2	[25], [26]	CS, SE CS, SE	MODE, GUID
	University of Stuttgart	1	[27]	CS, SE	METY
<i>Hungary</i>	Obuda University	1	[28]	CS, T&M	TOOL
<i>India</i>	Vellore Institute of Technology	1	[29]	CS, AI	FRAM
<i>Israel</i>	Ben Gurion University	1	[30]	CS, AI	MTOO
<i>Korea</i>	Sookmyung Women's University	1	[31]	CS, H&A	TOOL
<i>Poland</i>	Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center	1	[32]	CS, SE	TOOL
<i>Russia</i>	Saint Petersburg State University	1	[33]	CS, H&A	TOOL
	Perm State University	1	[34]	CS, T&M	TOOL
	National Research Centre Kurchatov Institute	1	[35]	CS, T&M	MODE
<i>Spain</i>	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	2	[36], [37]	CS, SE CS, T&M	MODE, MODE
<i>Switzerland</i>	University of Zurich	1	[38]	CS, IA	GUID
<i>United Kingdom</i>	Keele University	2	[39], [40]	CS, SE CS, SE	METH, GUID
	The University of Wales	1	[41]	MS	MODE
	Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute	1	[42]	M&CB	TOOL
	Stanford University	2	[43], [44]	CS, AI CS, AI	TOOL, TOOL
<i>USA</i>	Indiana University Bloomington	1	[45]	CS, H&A	TOOL
	Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute	1	[46]	BRM	MODE
	Siemens Corporate Research	1	[47]	CS, SE	FTOO
	University of Southern California	1	[48]	CS, IS	TOOL
	UC Santa Cruz Computer Science Department - Systems Research Lab	1	[49]	CS, SE	TOOL
	Purdue University	1	[50]	CS, IA	FRAM
	University of Texas at El Paso	1	[51]	EM	GUID

Stevens Institute of Technology	1	[52]	CS, IA	TOOL
Southern Methodist University	1	[53]	CS, T&M	GUID
National Institute of Standards and Technology	1	[54]	MA	GUID

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